

Low Density Polyethylene/MgO Nanocomposites as Insulation for HVDC Cables

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1. General Introduction

Since the electric power demand is rapidly increasing in an urban area in the world, a long distance dc power transmission becomes more and more important. To develop the long distance power transmission cable, the insulating materials with good performance under a high electric field are urgently needed^[1]. In recent years, polymer nanocomposites (PN), a new insulating material, have been attracting more and more attentions of researchers. Polymer nanocomposites are defined as the second generation of what we call filled resins in the insulation engineering. A few percent of nano-sized inorganic filler added into polymer can improve various properties significantly, compared with a large amount (the order of 50 wt%) of micro-sized filler^[2]. Many research results suggest that nano-MgO are selected as the inorganic filler of polymer nanocomposites for high voltage direct current (HVDC) cables. The LDPE/MgO nano-composite material, which is made of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and nano-sized magnesium oxide (MgO) filler, is one of such newly developed materials. The LDPE/MgO nanocomposites bear a higher breakdown strength^[3] and lower space charge accumulation^[4] under high dc stress than those of LDPE.

Space charge distribution in insulating materials for the dc power cables under high dc stress is very crucial. When a dc voltage is applied to the polymer insulating material, the space charge accumulates in it and consequently, the electric field in the insulating material is sometimes enhanced, which may result in an

unexpected breakdown. Many research works have proved that nano-MgO can suppress space charge formation in the LDPE efficiently. However, most of them focused on the electric properties and suppression mechanism. The preparation process of LDPE/MgO nanocomposites has not been mentioned yet. In this paper, different kinds of silane coupling agent treated nano-MgO influence on space charge distribution of LDPE nanocomposites under high electric field were measured.

2. Experimental

The purity of employed nano-MgO is 99.9%. The average diameter of MgO nano-filler is 50 nm. The surface of nano-MgO was treated with three different silane coupling agents described in Table 1. The master batch with 10 phr MgO was firstly prepared using twin-screw extruder. The master batch was then diluted to the certain concentration of 1, 2, 3 and 5 phr. Nano-scale observation of the nano-MgO dispersion state in LDPE was carried out by TEM. Fig. 1(a) and 1(b) are TEM photographs of LDPE with 10 phr and 3 phr nano-MgO-I, respectively. The specimens were prepared by cryogenic microtoming in liquid nitrogen. The investigations on thin section cut from the strands (Fig. 1 (a)) showed some agglomerate with size less than 10 μm at 10 phr. Fig. 1(b) shows MgO has the good dispersion and the dominance of well separated at 3 phr. The other two MgO-a and MgO-v show the same dispersion state in the LDPE with different addition. The composite were hot press to films for the test sample. Then, the films were hot treated at 353 k in vacuum baking oven for 48 h before test. The samples for DC breakdown are around 500 μm in thickness and for space charge are around 300 μm . PEA measurements are carried out

for basically 10 minutes at 25°C temperatures and then short-circuited. samples sandwiched between an Al electrode and a semiconductive (SC) polymer electrode sensor attached to the Al electrode.

Table 1. Description of the silane coupling agents.

	Description	
1	Long chain alkyl silane	MgO-l
2	Vinyl and olefin functional silane	MgO-v
3	Amino functional silane	MgO-a

Figure 1. TEM micrographs of extruded strands of LDPE with (a) 10 phr and (b) 3 phr MgO.

3. Results and discussion

The influence of the MgO nano-filler content on DC impulse breakdown strength is given in Fig. 2. The breakdown strength was calculated by dividing the breakdown voltage by the film thickness. The error bar and the signs are standard deviation and the average of about 5 samples, respectively. The breakdown strength measured under a dc electric field increased firstly and then decreased with the increase of MgO content. It is suggested that MgO clearly improve the breakdown strength of the LDPE. Compared with three kinds of nano-MgO treated with different silane coupling agent added at 5phr, it demonstrate the breakdown strength of MgO-l/LDPE is little more higher than the others.

Figure 2. The influence of the MgO nano-filler content on DC breakdown strength.

Figure 3. Space charge distribution of LDPE nanocomposites under the electric field of 40 kV/mm.

Fig.3(a) shows a typical measurement result of the space charge behavior in pure LDPE under an electric field of 40 kV/mm at room temperature^[1]. It can be clearly seen that a huge amount of positive packet-like charge are injected from the anode into LDPE, and after that a negative packet-like charge is injected from the cathode. There is a lot of positive and negative space charge appearing in the middle of the sample.

Fig. 3(b) and 3(c) show the time dependent space charge behaviors in LDPE/MgO-l and LDPE/MgO-v under electric field of 40 kV/mm for 30 s and 10 minutes, respectively. We found that no packet-like charge is observed in all cases. Therefore, we concluded that the addition of 10 phr MgO filler to LDPE is effective to suppress the packet-like charge injection into bulk of sample using these two kinds of coupling agents. Fig. 3(d) gives the time dependent space charge behaviors in LDPE/MgO-a under electric field of 40 kV/mm for 30 s and 10

minutes, respectively. Unlike LDPE/MgO-l and LDPE/MgO-v, there is still a little space charge distributing among the sample.

Space charge within a sample under a high electric field is generally more easily observed after the sample is short-circuited than during the voltage application as long as the charge has a relatively long life^[5]. Fig. 4(a), 4(b), 4(c) and 4(d) show space charge distribution of pure LDPE and its nanocomposites (MgO-l, MgO-v and MgO-a) when these samples are short-circuited. We can clearly see that a lot of space charge exist in the pure LDPE sample. The fact that the space charge amount is in the order, pure LDPE>LDPE/MgO-a>LDPE/MgO-v>LDPE/MgO-l, is clearly demonstrated.

Figure 4. Space charge distribution of pure LDPE and its nanocomposites when samples are short-circuited.

4. Conclusion

The electric properties of three different kinds of silane coupling agent treated MgO nanocomposites (LDPE/MgO) were studied through the DC breakdown and PEA tests.

(1) The nano-MgO effectively restricted the homo charge injection from the electrode.

(2) Long chain alkyl silane treated MgO improves LDPE insulation properties more effectively than MgO treated with vinyl, olefin and amino functional silanes.

References

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